

SURFACE STRESS EFFECT IN THIN FILMS WITH NANOSCALE ROUGHNESS

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1 Introduction

During the last decade, a lot of interest has been focused on the surface defect formation. It was shown that a diverse range of defects may arise due to different external influences: vacations and interstitials, dislocations, disclinations, crystal twins, nanoclusters, microcracks. Almost all of the defects associated with structural and phase transition in stress concentration area. Analyzing a sinusoidal surface perturbation of a stressed solid, Gao [1] has shown that even a slightly undulating surface can generate significant stress concentration to cause fracture before the bulk stress reaches a critical level. However, the derived solution is inapplicable to nanoscale roughness. It has recently been shown that surface effect should be taken into account for analysis of nanostructures on the solid surface [2]. In the current study, we generalized an analytical solution of a plane strain problem for a stressed film coating with slightly undulating surface [3] taking into account surface elasticity and residual surface stress.

2 Problem formulation

We consider 2D problem for an isotropic film/substrate system under external loads. The substrate is modeled as an elastic half-plane Ω_2 with planar surface Γ_2 . And the film is modeled as a strip Ω_1 of thickness h_0 . The film surface Γ_1 has an arbitrary small perturbation

$$\Gamma_1 = \{z_1 : z_1 = x_1 + i[h_0 + \varepsilon f(x_1)]\} \quad (1)$$

where $f(x_1 + a) = f(x_1)$, $\max|f(x_1)| = a$, $|f'(x_1)| < 1/\varepsilon$, $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$.

According to the theory of surface elasticity [5], the surface phases Γ_i are idealized as a pre-stressed

elastic membranes coherently bonded to the boundary of the bulk material. Constitutive equations of linear elasticity for bulk Ω_i and surface Γ_i phases in the case of the plane strain problem are respectively

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{mn} &= (\lambda_i + 2\mu_i)\varepsilon_{mn} + \lambda_i\varepsilon_{ii} \\ \sigma_{ii} &= (\lambda_i + 2\mu_i)\varepsilon_{ii} + \lambda_i\varepsilon_{nn} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_{nt} = 2\mu_i\varepsilon_{nt}, \quad z \in \Omega_i$$

$$\tau_{tt} = \gamma_0^i + (\lambda_s^i + 2\mu_s^i - \gamma_0^i)\varepsilon_{tt}^s, \quad z \in \Gamma_i \quad (3)$$

In eqs. (3), λ_s^i, μ_s^i are the surface constants similar to the bulk Lamé constants λ_i, μ_i in eqs. (2); γ_0^i are the residual surface stresses.

In general case, an external surface load acts on the curved boundary Γ_1 of the strip

$$q(z_1) = q(z_1 + a), \quad \int_{z_1 - a/2}^{z_1 + a/2} q(t)dt = -iP, \quad P = P_1 + iP_2 \quad (4)$$

and satisfies the Hölder condition on Γ_1 .

The following conditions are realized at infinity

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{x_2 \rightarrow -\infty} (\sigma_{22} - i\sigma_{12}) &= -i\frac{P}{a}, \\ \lim_{x_2 \rightarrow -\infty} \omega &= \omega^\infty, \quad \lim_{x_2 \rightarrow -\infty} \sigma_{11} = \sigma_{11}^\infty \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

here ω is the rotation angle of material particles. Conditions of the mechanical equilibrium on curved surface Γ_1 and planar interface Γ_2 are described by the generalized Young-Laplace equations [4] which take the following form in two-dimensional case

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_n(z_1) &= q(z_1) + T^s \tau_n(z_1), \quad z_1 \in \Gamma_1 \\ \Delta \sigma_n(z_2) &= \sigma_n^+ - \sigma_n^- = -i \frac{\partial \tau_{11}(z_2)}{\partial x_1}, \quad z_2 \in \Gamma_2\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

Here $T^s(\cdot) = \kappa \cdot (\cdot) - i \frac{1}{h} \frac{d(\cdot)}{dx_1}$, $\sigma_n = \sigma_{nn} + i\sigma_{nt}$,

$$\sigma_n^\pm = \lim_{z \rightarrow z_2 \pm i0} \sigma_n(z).$$

Local principal curvature κ and metric coefficient h are defined as

$$\begin{aligned}\kappa &= \frac{\varepsilon f''(x_1)}{\left(1 + \varepsilon^2 f'^2(x_1)\right)^{3/2}}, \\ h &= \frac{1}{\left(1 + \varepsilon^2 f'^2(x_1)\right)^{1/2}}\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

Since we assumed that surface phases and the substrate are coherent, the displacement field is continuous

$$\begin{aligned}\lim_{z \rightarrow z_1} u(z) &= u(z_1), \quad u = u_1 + iu_2, \quad z_1 \in \Gamma_1 \\ \Delta u(z_2) &= u^+ - u^- = 0, \quad u^\pm = \lim_{z \rightarrow z_2 \pm i0} u(z), \quad z_2 \in \Gamma_2\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

3 Superposition method

Following superposition principle [3], we represent the solution $\tau_n(z_k), \sigma_n(z), u(z)$ of the boundary value problem (2)–(8) as

$$G(z, \eta_k) = G_1(z, \eta_1) \delta_{k1} + G_2(z, \eta_k), \quad z \in \Omega_k \quad (9)$$

where the functions $G(z, \eta_k), G_1(z, \eta_1), G_2(z, \eta_k)$ are respectively equal to $\sigma_n(z, \eta_k), \sigma_n^1(z, \eta_1), \sigma_n^2(z, \eta_k)$ for $\eta_k = 1$ and $-2\mu_k du/dz, -2\mu_k du^2/dz, -2\mu_1 du^1/dz$ for $\eta_k = -\kappa_k$, $k = 1, 2$ with $\kappa_k = 3 - 4\nu_k$ for the plane strain; ν_k, μ_k are Poisson's ratio and the shear modulus of the phase Ω_k respectively; δ_{k1} is the Kronecker delta.

In equation (9), σ_n^1, u^1 are the vectors of stresses and displacements arisen in a homogeneous half-plane Ω with wavy boundary Γ_1 and elastic properties of the layer Ω_1 under the action of unknown self-balanced surface load p and surface stress ν

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_n^1(z_1) &= p(\zeta_1) + T^s \nu(\zeta_1), \quad z_1 \in \Gamma_1 \\ p(\zeta_1) &= p(\zeta_1 + a), \quad \int_{\zeta_1 - a/2}^{\zeta_1 + a/2} p(t) dt = 0\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

while the rotation angle of the material particle and stresses at infinity are equal to zero at infinity.

σ_n^2, u^2 are the vectors of stresses and displacements arisen in two-component plane $D_1 \cup D_2$ ($D_2 = \Omega_2$) with elastic properties of the phases Ω_1, Ω_2 and unknown jumps of tractions $\Delta \sigma_n^2$ and displacements Δu^2 at the rectilinear interface Γ_2 under conditions (5) at infinity.

Passing to the limit as $z \rightarrow z_1 \in \Gamma_1$ in (9) and taking into account the boundary conditions (6), (8), (10), and Hooke's law (2), (3), we obtain the following system of the boundary equations for the unknown functions p, ν, τ_n

$$\begin{aligned}p(\zeta_1) + T^s \nu(\zeta_1) + \sigma_n^2(z_1) &= q(z_1) + T^s \tau_n(z_1), \\ \Delta \sigma_n^2(z_2) &= i\tau'_{11}(z_2) - \sigma_n^1(z_2), \quad \Delta u^2(z_2) = -u^1(z_2), \\ \tau_n(z_k) &= \gamma_0^k + \left(\lambda_s^k + 2\mu_s^k - \gamma_0^k\right) \varepsilon_n(z_k), \\ \zeta_1 &= z_1 - ih_0, \quad z_i \in \Gamma_i\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

Thus, the original problem is reduced to solving the system of boundary equations (11).

4 Solution of half-space problem based on surface elasticity

According to [2, 3, 5, 6] the stress vector σ_n^1 and the displacement vector u^1 are related to Goursat-Kolosov's complex potentials Φ and Υ

$$\begin{aligned}G_1(z, \eta_1) &= \eta_1 \Phi(\zeta) + \overline{\Phi(\zeta)} - \left(\Upsilon(\bar{\zeta}) + \overline{\Phi(\zeta)} - (\zeta - \bar{\zeta}) \overline{\Phi'(\zeta)}\right) e^{-2i\alpha}, \quad \text{Im} \zeta < \varepsilon f(x_1)\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

where α is the angle between the direction of the area element with the normal \mathbf{n} and the real axis ξ_1 of the complex variable $\zeta = \xi_1 + i\xi_2 = z - ih_0$. Functions $\Phi(\zeta)$ and $\Upsilon(\zeta)$ are holomorphic in the domain Ω with the boundary Γ_1 and domain

$B = \{ \zeta : \xi_1 \in \mathbb{R}^1, \xi_2 > -\varepsilon f(x_1) \}$ with the boundary
 $L = \{ \zeta : \zeta = \bar{\zeta}_1, \zeta_1 \in \Gamma_1 \}$, correspondingly.

The values of the functions $\Phi(\zeta), Y(\zeta)$ at infinity follow from zero conditions, similar to (5)

$$\lim_{x_2 \rightarrow -\infty} \Phi(\zeta) = \lim_{x_2 \rightarrow +\infty} Y(\zeta) = 0 \quad (13)$$

Taking into account the boundary condition (10), pass to the limit in equation (12) under $\zeta \rightarrow \zeta_1$ and $\alpha \rightarrow \alpha_1$. Then we obtain

$$\Phi^-(\zeta_1) + \overline{\Phi^-(\zeta_1)} - \left(Y^+(\bar{\zeta}_1) + \overline{\Phi^-(\zeta_1)} - \left(\zeta_1 - \bar{\zeta}_1 \right) \overline{\Phi'^-(\zeta_1)} \right) e^{-2i\alpha_1} = p(\zeta_1) + T^s v(\zeta_1), \quad (14)$$

$$\Phi^-(\zeta_1) = \lim_{\zeta \rightarrow \zeta_1 - i0} \Phi(\zeta), \quad Y^+(\zeta_1) = \lim_{\zeta \rightarrow \zeta_1 - i0} Y(\bar{\zeta})$$

Here α_1 is the angle between the positive direction of the tangent to Γ_1 at the point ζ_1 and the axis ξ_1 . In accordance with the perturbation technique [1-3, 5], we expand functions $\Phi(\zeta), Y(\zeta), p(\zeta_1)$ and $v(\zeta_1)$ in power series of the small parameter ε

$$\Phi(\zeta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon^n}{n!} \Phi_n(\zeta), \quad Y(\zeta) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon^n}{n!} Y_n(\zeta), \quad (15)$$

$$p(\zeta_1) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon^n}{n!} p_n(\zeta_1), \quad v(\zeta_1) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\varepsilon^n}{n!} v_n(\zeta_1)$$

and boundary values of functions Φ_n, Y_n on Γ_1 and functions p_n, v_n in the corresponding Taylor series near the straight line $\text{Im } \zeta = 0$, treating the real variable $\xi_1 = x_1$ as a parameter

$$\Phi_n^-(\zeta_1) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{[i\varepsilon f(x_1)]^m}{m!} \Phi_n^{(m)-}(x_1), \quad (16)$$

$$Y_n^+(\bar{\zeta}_1) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{[i\varepsilon f(x_1)]^m}{m!} Y_n^{(m)+}(x_1),$$

$$p_n(\zeta_1) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{[i\varepsilon f(x_1)]^m}{m!} p_n^{(m)}(x_1) \quad (17)$$

$$v_n(\zeta_1) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{[i\varepsilon f(x_1)]^m}{m!} v_n^{(m)}(x_1)$$

Substituting (15)–(17) into (14) and equating the coefficients of the power ε^n ($n = 0, 1, \dots$), we obtain the following sequence of boundary equations

$$Y_n^+(x_1) - \Phi_n^-(x_1) = i\tau_n'(x_1) - p_n(x_1) + F_n(x_1) \quad (18)$$

where the functions $F_n(x_1)$ are known at the n -th approximation step. For the zeroth-order and first-order approximations, we can write

$$F_0(x_1) = 0,$$

$$F_1(x_1) = if'(x_1) \left[\Phi_0^-(x_1) + Y_0^{'+}(x_1) + 2\overline{\Phi_0^-(x_1)} \right] + 2if'(x_1) \left[Y_0^+(x_1) + \overline{\Phi_0^-(x_1)} \right] - f(x_1)v_0''(x_1) + -f''(x_1)v_0(x_1) - if'(x_1)p_0'(x_1) \quad (19)$$

Here we used the expansion

$$\frac{1}{1+i\varepsilon f'(x_1)} = 1 + 2 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-i\varepsilon f'(x_1))^{n+1} \quad (20)$$

which holds for $|\varepsilon f'(x_1)| < 1$ and equality

$$e^{-2i\alpha} = 1 - \frac{2i\varepsilon f'(x_1)}{1+i\varepsilon f'(x_1)} \quad (21)$$

After considering auxiliary functions Θ_n holomorphic outside the line $\text{Im } \zeta = 0$

$$\Theta_n(\zeta) = \begin{cases} Y_n(\zeta), & \text{Im } \zeta > 0 \\ \Phi_n(\zeta), & \text{Im } \zeta < 0 \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

we obtain the Riemann-Hilbert problem [6] the solution of which is

$$\Theta_n(\zeta) = \Theta_n^{um}(\zeta) + \Theta_n^{kn}(\zeta) = \left[\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{iv'_n(t)}{t-\zeta} dt - \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{p_n(t)}{t-\zeta} dt \right] + \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{F_n(t)}{t-\zeta} dt \quad (23)$$

As the displacement needs to be continuous across the phase interfaces, we can write the equation for finding the surface stress ν

$$\nu(z_1) = \gamma_0^1 + (\lambda_s^1 + 2\mu_s^1 - \gamma_0^1) \varepsilon_n^1(z_1) \quad (24)$$

Due to expansions (15)-(17), equation (24) reduces to the following

$$\nu_n(x_1) - W_1 \operatorname{Re} \left[Y_n^+(x_1) + \kappa_1 \Phi_n^-(x_1) \right] = H_n^1(x_1) \quad (25)$$

where $W_1 = \frac{\lambda_s^1 + 2\mu_s^1 - \gamma_0^1}{2\mu_1}$. For the zeroth-order and first-order approximations, we have

$$\begin{aligned} H_0^1(x_1) &= \gamma_0^1, \\ H_1^1(x_1) &= -W_1 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ if(x_1) \left[-\kappa_1 \Phi_0^-(x_1) + Y_0'^+(x_1) + 2\overline{\Phi_0^-(x_1)} \right] + 2if'(x_1) \left[Y_0^+(x_1) + \overline{\Phi_0^-(x_1)} \right] \right\} - if(x_1)v_0'(x_1) \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

5 Interface stress model in two-component plane

In accordance with [3, 5, 6], the stress-strain state of two component plane are determined by the formula

$$G_2(z, \eta_k) = \eta_k \Lambda_k(z) + \overline{\Lambda_k(z)} - \left(Z_k(z) + \overline{\Lambda_k(z)} - (z - \bar{z}) \overline{\Lambda_k'(z)} \right) e^{-2i\alpha}, \quad z \in D_k \quad (27)$$

where functions $\Lambda_k(z)$ are holomorphic in D_k and $Z_k(z)$ are holomorphic in D_{3-k} ($k=1, 2$).

By setting $\operatorname{Im} z \rightarrow \pm\infty$ at $\alpha=0$ and $\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2}$ in (27) and taking into account conditions (5), we

obtain the values of the functions $\Lambda_k(z)$ and $Z_k(z)$ at infinity

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{|\operatorname{Im} z| \rightarrow \infty} \Lambda_k(z) &= a_k^k, \quad \lim_{|\operatorname{Im} z| \rightarrow \infty} Z_j(z) = a_j^k, \\ a_k^k &= \frac{\sigma_{11}^{k\infty} + \sigma_{22}^{k\infty}}{4} + i \frac{2\mu_k}{\eta_k + 1} \omega_k^\infty, \\ a_j^j - a_j^k &= -\frac{iP}{\lambda}, \quad z \in D_k, \quad (j, k = 1, 2, j \neq k) \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Let $z \rightarrow z_2 \in \Gamma_2$ in (27) and $\alpha=0$. Taking into account conditions (11) on the interface Γ_2 , we derive two equations for the boundary values of functions Λ_k and Z_k , which are written in the form of the following general equation

$$\begin{aligned} [m_1 Z_2(z_2) + m_2 \eta_1 \Lambda_1(z_2)] - [m_2 Z_1(z_2) + m_1 \eta_2 \Lambda_2(z_2)] &= \Delta \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Equation (29) is derived from the second jump condition in (11) with $m_k = \eta_k = 1$, $\Delta = i\tau_{11}'(z_2) - \sigma_n^1(z_2)$ and from the third jump condition in (11) with $m_k = \mu_k$, $\eta_k = -\kappa_k$, $\Delta = -2\mu_1 \mu_2 u^{1'}(z_2)$.

Introduce auxiliary functions $\Sigma(z)$ and $V(z)$ holomorphic outside the straight line Γ_2 as follows

$$\Sigma(z) = \begin{cases} Z_2(z) + \Lambda_1(z), & \operatorname{Im} z > 0 \\ Z_1(z) + \Lambda_2(z), & \operatorname{Im} z < 0 \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

$$V(z) = \begin{cases} \mu_1 Z_2(z) - \mu_2 \kappa_1 \Lambda_1(z), & \operatorname{Im} z > 0 \\ \mu_2 Z_1(z) - \mu_1 \kappa_2 \Lambda_2(z), & \operatorname{Im} z < 0 \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

then equations (29) reduce to Riemann-Hilbert problems for boundary values of functions Σ and V

$$\Sigma^+(x_1) - \Sigma^-(x_1) = i\tau_{11}'(x_1) - \sigma_n^1(x_1) \quad (32)$$

$$V^+(x_1) - V^-(x_1) = -2\mu_1 \mu_2 u^{1'}(x_1) \quad (33)$$

Here $\Sigma^\pm(x_1) = \lim_{\operatorname{Im} z \rightarrow \pm 0} \Sigma(z)$, $V^\pm(x_1) = \lim_{\operatorname{Im} z \rightarrow \pm 0} V(z)$.

According to [6], the solutions of Riemann-Hilbert boundary problems (32) and (33) take the form

$$\Sigma(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{i\tau'_{11}(t)}{t-z} dt - \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\sigma_n^1(t)}{t-z} dt + s \quad (34)$$

$$V(z) = \frac{\mu_1\mu_2}{\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{(w^1)'(t)}{t-z} dt + v \quad (35)$$

where $v = \mu_2 a_1^2 - \mu_1 \kappa_2 a_2^2 = \mu_1 a_2^1 - \mu_2 \kappa_1 a_1^1$,

$$s = a_1^2 + a_2^2 = a_2^1 + a_1^1.$$

The expressions of complex potentials Λ_k and Z_k in terms of functions $\Sigma(z)$ and $V(z)$ are derived from equations (30) and (31)

$$\Lambda_k(z) = \frac{\mu_k \Sigma(z) - V(z)}{\mu_k + \mu_l \kappa_k}, \quad (36)$$

$$Z_k(\bar{z}) = \frac{\mu_k \kappa_l \Sigma(\bar{z}) + V(\bar{z})}{\mu_l + \mu_k \kappa_l}$$

Substituting (12) into (34) and (35) for $\alpha = 0$ and taking into account properties of Cauchy type integral, one can write

$$\Sigma(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{i\tau'_{11}(t)}{t-z} dt + s + \begin{cases} \Upsilon(z + ih_0) + 2ih_0 \overline{\Phi'(z + ih_0)}, & \text{Im } z > 0 \\ \Phi(z - ih_0), & \text{Im } z < 0 \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

$V(z) = v +$

$$+ \mu_2 \begin{cases} \Upsilon(z + ih_0) + 2ih_0 \overline{\Phi'(z + ih_0)}, & \text{Im } z > 0 \\ -\kappa_1 \Phi(z - ih_0), & \text{Im } z < 0 \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

Now we can express the solution $G_2(z, \eta_k)$ in the terms of the functions $\Phi(z)$ and $\Upsilon(z)$

$$G_2(z, \eta_k) = M_k(\Phi, \Upsilon, z, \alpha, \eta_k) + K_k(I_\tau, z, \alpha, \eta_k) + G_2^{k\infty}(\alpha, \eta_k), \quad z \in \Omega_k \quad (39)$$

$$M_1(\Phi, \Upsilon, z, \alpha, \eta_1) = \eta_1 T_{11} \Xi(w) + T_{11} \overline{\Xi(w)} (1 - e^{-2i\alpha}) - T_{12} e^{-2i\alpha} \Phi(\bar{w}) + (z - \bar{z}) T_{11} \overline{\Xi'(w)} e^{-2i\alpha} \quad (40)$$

$$K_1(I_\tau, z, \alpha, \eta_1) = \eta_1 Q_{11} I_\tau(z) + Q_{11} \overline{I_\tau(z)} (1 - e^{-2i\alpha}) + (z - \bar{z}) Q_{11} \overline{I_\tau'(z)} e^{-2i\alpha} \quad (41)$$

$$M_2(\Phi, \Upsilon, z, \alpha, \eta_2) = \eta_2 T_{22} \Phi(\zeta) + T_{22} \overline{\Phi(\zeta)} (1 - e^{-2i\alpha}) - T_{21} e^{-2i\alpha} \Xi(\bar{\zeta}) + (z - \bar{z}) T_{22} \overline{\Phi'(\zeta)} e^{-2i\alpha} \quad (42)$$

$$K_2(I_\tau, z, \alpha, \eta_2) = -Q_{21} I_\tau(\bar{z}) e^{-2i\alpha} \quad (43)$$

where $I_\tau(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{i\tau'_{11}(t)}{t-z} dt$, $w = z + ih_0$,

$$\Xi(t) = \Upsilon(t) + 2ih_0 \overline{\Phi'(t)}, \quad T_{11} = \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_2}{\mu_1 + \mu_2 \kappa_1},$$

$$T_{12} = \frac{\mu_1 \kappa_2 - \mu_2 \kappa_1}{\mu_2 + \mu_1 \kappa_2}, \quad T_{22} = 1 - T_{12}, \quad T_{21} = 1 - T_{11},$$

$$Q_{11} = \frac{\mu_1}{\mu_1 + \mu_2 \kappa_1}, \quad Q_{21} = 1 - Q_{11},$$

$$G_2^{k\infty}(\alpha, \eta_k) = \eta_k a_k^k + \overline{a_k^k} (1 - e^{-2i\alpha}) - a_j^k e^{-2i\alpha}, \quad k, j = 1, 2; k \neq j.$$

Taking into account the 3rd boundary condition from (11) and the solution (9), one can write the equation for finding surface stress $\tau_{11}(z_2)$ at the interface

$$\tau_{11}(x_1) = \gamma_0^2 + W_2 \text{Re} G_2(z_2, -\kappa_2) \quad (44)$$

6 System of integral equations for n -th order approximation

Substitution of (39) and (44) into first equation of (11) will give boundary condition in terms of the functions $\Phi(z)$ and $\Upsilon(z)$

$$T^s v(\zeta_1) - T^s \tau_{11}(z_1) + M_1(\Phi, \Upsilon, z_1, \alpha, 1) + K_1(I_\tau, z_1, \alpha, 1) + p(\zeta_1) = q(\zeta_1) - G_2^{1\infty}(\alpha, 1) \quad (45)$$

where surface stress $\tau_{11}(z_1)$ is defined from boundary condition (11) and solution (9)

$$\tau_{11}(z_1) = \gamma_0^1 + W_1 \text{Re} [G_1(z_1, -\kappa_1) + G_2(z_1, -\kappa_1)] \quad (46)$$

Thus, the solution of original problem (1)–(8) is reduced to the system of integral equations (24), (44)–(46) for the unknown functions $p(\zeta_1)$,

$v(\zeta_1)$, $\tau_{11}(x_1)$ and $\tau_{in}(z_1)$.

Since $\zeta_1 = z_1 - ih_0 = x_1 + i\varepsilon f(x_1)$, we can use the perturbation method to obtain the explicit expressions for corresponding functions in all order approximations [1-3, 5]. By analogy with (15)–(17), we represent all the functions in (44), (45) and (46) as a power series in ε with unknown coefficients and expand the boundary values of these coefficients on Γ_1 in the corresponding Taylor series. Equating the coefficients of the powers ε^n , we obtain the following system of integral equations for n -th order approximation in the unknown expansion coefficients $p_n(x_1)$, $v_n(x_1)$, $\tau_{11n}(x_1)$, $\tau_{in}(x_1)$

$$v_n(x_1) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{11}(x_1, t) p_n(t) dt - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{11}(x_1, t) i v_n'(t) dt = Y_n^1(x_1) \quad (47)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{11n}(x_1) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{21}(x_1, t) p_n(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{22}(x_1, t) \overline{p_n(t)} dt - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{21}(x_1, t) i v_n'(t) dt - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{22}(x_1, t) i \overline{v_n'(t)} dt + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{23}(x_1, t) \tau_{11n}'(t) dt = Y_n^2(x_1) \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

$$\begin{aligned} p_n(x_1) - i v_n'(x_1) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{31}(x_1, t) p_n(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{32}(x_1, t) \overline{p_n(t)} dt - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{31}(x_1, t) i v_n'(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{32}(x_1, t) i \overline{v_n'(t)} dt + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{33}(x_1, t) i \tau_{11n}'(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{34}(x_1, t) i \overline{\tau_{11n}'(t)} dt + i \tau_{in}'(x_1) = Y_n^3(x_1) \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{in}(x_1) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [X_{11}(x_1, t) + X_{31}(x_1, t)] p_n(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{22}(x_1, t) \overline{p_n(t)} dt - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} [X_{11}(x_1, t) + X_{31}(x_1, t)] v_n'(t) dt - \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{32}(x_1, t) \overline{v_n'(t)} dt + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{33}(x_1, t) \tau_{11n}'(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X_{34}(x_1, t) \overline{\tau_{11n}'(t)} dt = Y_n^4(x_1) \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

The kernels X_{ij} can be written as

$$X_{11}(x_1, t) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \frac{W_1(\kappa_1 + 1)}{t - x_1} \quad (51)$$

$$X_{21}(x_1, t) = -\frac{1}{2\pi i} \frac{W_2(\kappa_1 + 1)(\kappa_2 T_{22} - T_{21})}{t - x_1} \quad (52)$$

$$X_{22}(x_1, t) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{W_2(\kappa_1 + 1) h_0 T_{21}}{(t - x_1)^2} \quad (53)$$

$$X_{23}(x_1, t) = -\frac{1}{2\pi i} \frac{W_2(\kappa_1 + 1) Q_{21}}{t - x_1} \quad (54)$$

$$X_{31}(x_1, t) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left[\frac{T_{12}}{t - w_0} - \frac{T_{11}}{t - w_0} - \frac{8h_0^2 T_{11}}{(t - w_0)^3} \right] \quad (55)$$

$$X_{32}(x_1, t) = \frac{T_{11}h_0}{\pi} \left[\frac{1}{(t-w_0)^2} + \frac{1}{(t-w_0)^2} \right] \quad (56)$$

$$X_{33}(x_1, t) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \frac{Q_{11}}{t-x_1} \quad (57)$$

$$X_{34}(x_1, t) = \frac{h_0}{\pi} \frac{Q_{11}}{(t-x_1)^2} \quad (58)$$

The right-hand sides $Y_n^i(x_1)$ of the equations (47)–(50) for the zeroth-order and first-order approximations are equal to

$$Y_0^1(x_1) = \gamma_0^1,$$

$$Y_1^1(x_1) = H_1^1(x_1) - W_1 \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1-\kappa_1}{2} F_1(x_1) - \frac{\kappa_1+1}{2\pi i} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{F_1(t)}{t-x_1} dt \right], \quad (59)$$

$$Y_0^2(x_1) = \gamma_0^2 + W_2 \operatorname{Re} G_2^{2\infty}(0, -\kappa_2), \quad (60)$$

$$Y_1^2(x_1) = \operatorname{Re} W_2 M_2(\Theta_1^{kn}, z_2, 0, -\kappa_2),$$

$$Y_0^3(x_1) = q_0(x_1) - G_2^{1\infty}(0, 1),$$

$$Y_1^3(x_1) = -if(x_1)p_0'(x_1) - f''(x_1)\nu_0(x_1) - f(x_1)\nu_0''(x_1) - 2if'(x_1)(\bar{a}_1^1 + a_2^1) - f''(x_1)\tau_{n0}(x_1) - f(x_1)\tau_{n0}''(x_1) - M_1(\Theta_1^{kn}(x_1), z_1, 0, 1) - if(x_1)M_1(\Theta_0'(x_1), z_1, 0, 1) - 2if'(x_1) \left[K_{22} \left\{ \overline{\Theta_0(w_0)} - 2ih_0\Theta_0'(\bar{w}_0) \right\} + K_{21}\Theta_0(\bar{w}_0) \right] - 2iK_{22} \left\{ f(x_1) - h_0f'(x_1) \right\} \times \left\{ \overline{\Theta_0'(w_0)} - 2ih_0\Theta_0''(\bar{w}_0) \right\}, \quad (61)$$

$$-if(x_1)M_1(\Theta_0'(x_1), z_1, 0, 1) - 2if'(x_1) \left[K_{22} \left\{ \overline{\Theta_0(w_0)} - 2ih_0\Theta_0'(\bar{w}_0) \right\} + K_{21}\Theta_0(\bar{w}_0) \right] - 2iK_{22} \left\{ f(x_1) - h_0f'(x_1) \right\} \times \left\{ \overline{\Theta_0'(w_0)} - 2ih_0\Theta_0''(\bar{w}_0) \right\},$$

$$Y_0^4(x_1) = \gamma_0^1 + W_1 \operatorname{Re} G_2^{1\infty}(0, -\kappa_1),$$

$$Y_1^4(x_1) = W_1 \operatorname{Re} \left\{ 2if'(x_1)(\bar{a}_1^1 + a_2^1) \right\} - if(x_1)\tau_{n0}'(x_1) - 2if(x_1)W_1 \operatorname{Re} \left[-M_1(\Theta_1^{kn}(x_1), z_1, 0, 1) - if(x_1)M_1(\Theta_0'(x_1), z_1, 0, 1) - 2if'(x_1) \left[K_{22} \left\{ \overline{\Theta_0(w_0)} - 2ih_0\Theta_0'(\bar{w}_0) \right\} + K_{21}\Theta_0(\bar{w}_0) \right] - 2iK_{22} \left\{ f(x_1) - h_0f'(x_1) \right\} \times \left\{ \overline{\Theta_0'(w_0)} - 2ih_0\Theta_0''(\bar{w}_0) \right\} + Y_1^1(x_1) \right] \quad (62)$$

Thus, relations (9), (12), (15), (22), (23), (39)–(44) and (46)–(50) give an algorithm for determining the stress-strain state of the film and the substrate for any degree of approximation. First of all, in the zeroth approximation, solving the system of integral equations (47)–(50) with the known right-hand sides Y_0^1, Y_0^2, Y_0^3 and Y_0^4 (59)–(62), we find functions the functions $p_0(x_1), \nu_0(x_1), \tau_{110}(x_1), \tau_{n0}(x_1)$. Then we use formulas (19), (23), (26) to find the functions $F_1(x_1), H_1^1(x_1)$ and $\Theta_0(x_1)$. After the functions $F_1(x_1), H_1^1(x_1)$ and $\Theta_0(x_1)$ is substituted into the system (47)–(50), its solution $p_1(x_1), \nu_1(x_1), \tau_{111}(x_1), \tau_{n1}(x_1)$ is found. The subsequent approximations are constructed according to the same scheme. As an example, we consider the film with the sinusoidal undulation of the surface. The stress-strain state is determined for the first-order approximation in case of a free film surface ($q = 0$) with only longitudinal stress σ_{11}^∞ acting in the substrate far from the interfacial boundary. The several computational results will be presented in the framework of the Micromechanics/Nanomechanics session of the ICCM-19 conference.

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References

- [1] H. Gao “Stress concentration at slightly undulating surfaces”. *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol. 39, pp. 443-458, 1991.
- [2] M. A. Grekov and S. A. Kostyrko “The effect of surface elasticity on morphological instability of a stressed solid”. *Proceedings of the 23rd international congress of theoretical and applied mechanics*, Beijing, China, MS06-056, p. 106, 2012.
- [3] M. A. Grekov, S. A. Kostyrko and Yu. I. Vikulina “Model of film coating with weakly curved surface”. *Mech. Solids*, Vol. 45, No. 6, pp. 778-788, 2010.
- [4] M. E. Gurtin and A. I. Murdoch “A continuum theory of elastic material surfaces”. *Arch. Ration. Mech. Anal.*, Vol. 57, pp. 291-323, 1975.
- [5] M.A. Grekov “*Singular plane problem of elasticity*”. Izd-vo St. Petersburg Univ., St. Petersburg, 2001[in Russian].
- [6] Muskhelishvili N.I. “*Some basic problems of mathematical theory of elasticity*”. Noordhoff, Groningen, 1963.